

Conductive Nanoparticle Enhancements for Structural Dielectric Capacitors

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Motivation

Concept of structural dielectric capacitors (SDCs)

- Energy stored by *interfacial polarization* of dielectric materials
- Carbon fibre reinforced composites (CFRP)-based electrodes
- Dielectric materials, e.g. polymer films and graphene oxide (GO) films

Research problem

- *Electrically insulating polymer* (e.g. epoxy) used for matrix of carbon fibre reinforced composite (CFRP)-based electrodes of SDC composites [1]

What we will deliver

- New insights into improving both the electrical and mechanical properties of SDC composite materials using *different concentrations* of gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) via *experiments*
- Revelation of the molecular level interactions of AuNPs and epoxy via *molecular dynamics (MD) simulation* [2]

Approach

Experimental section

TEM micrograph

- Particle size: ~2 to 5 nm
- Highly crystalline
- Evenly dispersed

Computational section (AuNPs/epoxy without carbon reinforcement) [2]

- Both hardener molecules and epoxy monomer absorbed on the surface of AuNP
- Increased the complexity
- Restricted localized movements

Concepts and Results

Electron transfer

- Electron tunneling effect
- Directly connected electron transfer network (at 0.5wt% and 1wt%)

Intrinsic toughening

- Ultimate stiffness of AuNPs: ~100GPa
- Stiffness of epoxy: ~3GPa

Electrical properties of AuNPs/SDC composites

- Electrical conductivity increased ~15 – 250%
- Specific capacitance increased ~10 – 150%
- Energy density increased ~15 – 55%
- Best performance achieved by 0.5wt% AuNP modified SDC

Experimental results on AuNPs/SDC composites

- Young's modulus increased ~1.5 – 7%
- Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) increased ~2 – 24%
- Best performance achieved by 1wt% AuNP modified SDC

Multifunctionality [3-6]

- ILSS vs Energy density
- Further enhancement via AuNPs addition

Discussion and Future Outlook

Conclusion

- This study highlighted the potential of the approach of doping CFRP-based electrodes with AuNPs to enhance both electrical and mechanical properties of SDC composites
- The optimum concentration of AuNPs in this study is 0.5wt%, at which some agglomeration occurs

Electric vehicle (EV) and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) applications

- High strength-to-weight ratio of AuNPs modified SDCs decrease vehicle weight by ~60% compared to conventional structural materials, such as steel and aluminum
- Energy storage ability could replace the conventional battery in vehicle, further decrease vehicle weight by ~15%

References

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